

Electrochemical investigations of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with bidentate Schiff base ligands in dimethylformamide

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Abstract : The electrochemical redox properties of bidentate Schiff base oxovanadium(IV) complexes viz. VO(sal-anl)₂ 1, VO(sal-tod)₂ 2, VO(hmp-and)₂ 3 and VO(hmp-oxime)₂ 4 have been studied in DMF/0.1 M TBAP using cyclic voltammetry at a Pt-working electrode. The electrochemistry of sal-anl and sal-tod ligands was also examined for the sake of comparison. Complexes 1 and 2 show almost similar electrochemistry. Oxidation of complex 2 is easier while reduction is difficult in comparison to 1 due to the +I inductive effect of electron-donating methyl group at the *para* position of toluidine. Complex 1 showed two irreversible anodic waves at $E_{pa_1} = +0.68$ V and $E_{pa_2} = +1.06$ V vs SCE and two irreversible cathodic peaks at $E_{pc_1} = -0.90$ V and $E_{pc_2} = -1.325$ V vs SCE followed by an irreversible anodic peak at $E_{pa'_2} = -0.42$ V at scan rate 100 mV s⁻¹. On the basis of CV results, it is concluded that in complexes 1 and 2, the redox processes a₁ and c₂ are metal-based while the redox processes a₂ and c₁ seem to be ligand-based. The CVs of 3 and 4 are also qualitatively similar. It is noteworthy that the anodic peak potential for the process VO^{2+/3+} shifted to more positive values in the sequence : VO(sal-tod)₂ → VO(sal-anl)₂ → VO(hmp-oxime)₂ → VO(hmp-and)₂.

Keywords : Cyclic voltammetry, electrochemistry, Schiff bases, vanadium complexes, biomimetic.

Introduction

Vanadium occurs in amavadine, a compound isolated from the mushroom *Amanita muscaria* and similar species. It is found in high concentrations in ascidians and is also present at the active sites of haloperoxidases (VHPOs) and the nitrogenase enzymes¹. Vanadium haloperoxidases (VHPOs) are found in a wide variety of marine algae and lichens² and catalyze the formation of a number of halogenated organic compounds and nitrogenases in the nitrogen fixing bacterium *Azotobacter*, which incorporates vanadium only (instead of molybdenum) into the corresponding cofactor or when molybdenum is deficient or after genetic manipulation³. More recently vanadium complexes have been found to be antidiabetic agent^{4a}. Bis-(maltolato)oxovanadium(IV), VO(ma)₂ has been found to be the first orally active insulin mimetic agent^{4b}.

It is noteworthy that the structure of R-group bonded to the imine nitrogen effects the coordination geometry of the complexes formed between the ON type bidentate Schiff bases and transition metal ions^{4c}. It is pertinent to

mention that vanadium(II,III) achieve hexacoordination⁵ exclusively for all the Schiff base complexes. The vacant coordination site(s) are occupied by molecule(s) of strong coordinating solvents.

ON type Schiff base

In our earlier publications⁶, we investigated the electrochemical/EPR spectral properties of oxovanadium(IV) complexes with Schiff bases and imine ligands. In this paper we report the electrochemical behaviour of some square pyramidal oxovanadium(IV) complexes, VO(SB)₂ with four different bidentate Schiff base (SB) ligands in DMF/0.1 M TBAP using cyclic voltammetry. The structures of Schiff base complexes, 1-4 utilized in the present investigation are given below :

Results and discussion

The redox behaviours of VO(sal-anl)_2 1, VO(sal-tod)_2 2, VO(hmp-and)_2 3 and VO(hmp-oxime)_2 4, were examined in DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP as the supporting electrolyte by cyclic voltammetry (CV) on a Pt-working electrode in the scan rate range 25 to 300 mV s^{-1} (sal-anl = salicylaldehyde-aniline; sal-tod = salicylaldehyde-*p*-toluidine; hmp-and = 2-hydroxy-5-methyl-propiofenone-*p*-anisidine; hmp-oxime = 2-hydroxyl-5-methyl-propiofenone-oxime). The electrochemical behaviours of sal-anl and sal-tod Schiff base ligands were also studied under identical experimental conditions for the sake of

comparison with their corresponding oxovanadium(IV) complexes 1 and 2, respectively. The CV results for complexes 1 to 4 and those of sal-anl and sal-tod ligands are presented in Table 1 at scan rate 50 mV s^{-1} . The cyclic voltammograms of complexes 1 and 3 at 50 mV s^{-1} are displayed in Fig. 1(a) and (b), respectively. A positive scan initiated at 0.0 V in the potential range from 0.0 to +1.25 V vs SCE shows two totally irreversible anodic waves at $E_{\text{pa}_1} = +0.660$ and $E_{\text{pa}_2} = +1.05$ V vs SCE, while a negative scan initiated at 0.0 V in the potential range 0.0 to -1.50 V revealed two irreversible reduction peaks at $E_{\text{pc}'_1} = -0.890$ V and $E_{\text{pc}_2} = -1.300$ V vs SCE

Table 1. CV data for 4 mM VO(SB)_2 complexes and SB ligands in DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP at 50 mV s^{-1}

Complex	E_{pa_1} (mV)	E_{pa_2} (V)	$E_{\text{pc}'_1}$ (mV)	E_{pc_2} (V)	$E_{\text{pa}'_2}$ (mV)
VO(sal-anl)_2 1	+660	+1.050	-890	-1.300	-490
VO(sal-tod)_2 2	+610	+0.990	-920	-1.360	-
VO(hmp-and)_2 3	+870	-	+220	-0.890	-485
VO(hmp-oxime)_2 4	+820	-	+270	-0.870	-155
SB Ligand		E_{pa} (V)	E_{pc} (mV)		$E_{\text{pa}'_1}$ (mV)
sal-anl		+1.030	-850		-590
sal-tod		+0.975	-900		-540

followed by an irreversible anodic peak at $E_{pa'_2} = -490$ mV in the reverse scan in the case of complex **1** (Table 1 and Fig. 1(a)). The CV of sal-anl ligand showed an irreversible anodic peak at $E_{pa} = +1.03$ V, while a negative scan indicated an irreversible reduction process at $E_{pc} = -850$ mV followed by an oxidation process at $E_{pa'_1} = -590$ mV vs SCE (Table 1). A perusal of Table 1 clearly shows that the electrochemical behaviour of complexes **1** and **2** is similar. On the basis of these observations it may be concluded that for complexes **1** and **2**, the first anodic peak a_1 and the second cathodic peak c_2 are due to metal-based redox processes (1) and (2) :

where, SB = sal-anl or sal-tod and S = solvent molecule.

Fig. 1. Cyclic voltammograms of : (a) 4 mM VO(sal-anl)₂ **1** and (b) VO(hmp-and)₂ **3** in DMF/0.1 M TBAP at 50 mV s⁻¹.

Furthermore, the anodic (E_{pa_2}) and cathodic ($E_{pc'_1}$) peak potentials for complexes **1** and **2** are comparable with E_{pa} and E_{pc} values, respectively for the uncomplexed respective ligand (sal-anl or sal-tod). This clearly indicates that anodic and cathodic peaks (a_2 and c_1') are ligand-centered. Expectedly, the anodic peak potential shifted to more positive values while the cathodic peak potential became more negative with increasing scan rate for the irreversible redox processes^{6,7} observed in these complexes. It is interesting to note that the anodic peak potentials (E_{pa_1}) are shifted cathodically (i.e. less positive) by ≈ 50 mV for **2**, indicating its easier oxidation in comparison to **1** (Table 1). This can be understood on the basis of +I inductive effect of electron-donating CH₃ group at the *para* position of toluidine, which causes greater electron-density on the metal atom in complex **2** relative to **1**. Thus, making the oxidation of **2** easier than **1**. On the contrary, cathodic peak potentials E_{pc_2} for these complexes show opposite trend, i.e. the reduction of complex **2** is more difficult than complex **1**. All these complexes **1-4** have been found to be square pyramidal in geometry involving N₂O₃ donor set on the basis of electronic and EPR spectral studies⁸.

The cyclic voltammograms of VO(hmp-and)₂ **3** and VO(hmp-oxime)₂ **4** are qualitatively very similar (Table 1). When the potential is swept from 0.0 to +1.20 V and back to 0.0 V, an irreversible anodic peak E_{pa_1} and its related cathodic peak $E_{pc'_1}$ appeared at +870 and +220 mV vs SCE, respectively. A negative scan initiated at 0.0 V in the potential range 0.0 to -1.4 V showed an irreversible cathodic peak E_{pc_2} at -890 mV and its related irreversible anodic peak $E_{pa'_2}$ at -485 mV. It should be noted that the anodic peak a_1 and cathodic peak c_2 did not have their complementary peaks, suggesting that the electrogenerated oxidized and reduced complex species, respectively at E_{pa_1} and E_{pc_2} , are unstable and these redox processes involve ECE mechanism^{6,7}. This is also supported by the appearance of cathodic peak c'_1 and anodic peak a'_2 .

It should be noted that the anodic peak potentials (E_{pa_1}) for the oxidation process VO^{2+/3+} (at 100 mV s⁻¹) are shifted to more positive values in the sequence : VO(sal-tod)₂ (+630 mV) → VO(sal-anl)₂ (+680 mV) → VO(hmp-oxime)₂ (+835 mV) → VO(hmp-and)₂ (+870); indicating that the oxidation of complex **3** is most difficult while complex **2** is easily oxidizable. In principle, the electronic effects (σ -donation and π -back-donation) in com-

bination with steric factors of the ligands and solution factors affect the redox potentials of complexes⁹.

Experimental

Electrochemical studies :

The experimental details of electrochemical measurements have already been described in our earlier publication¹⁰. All the potentials were measured using saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode. The platinum disc and platinum wire were used as working and auxiliary electrodes, respectively. Tetrabutyl ammonium perchlorate (TBAP, 0.1 M) received from Fluka, was used as the supporting electrolyte. High purity dimethylformamide (DMF) was obtained from E. Merck. All the experiments were performed at 25 ± 1 °C.

Preparation of bidentate Schiff base ligands :

Salicylaldehyde, 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone, aniline, *p*-toluidine, *p*-anisidine and hydroxylamine hydrochloride were purchased from Aldrich Chemical Co.

The Schiff bases were prepared by the condensation reaction of equimolar amounts of aldehyde/ketone and amine in ethanol media^{8b}. Ethanolic solution of salicylaldehyde/or 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone (hmp) and aniline (anl)/*p*-toluidine/*p*-anisidine were mixed together in 1 : 1 ratio. The contents were shaken vigorously and were refluxed for half an hour. Coloured Schiff bases were obtained in each case. These were washed thoroughly with water.

One mole of 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone (hmp) was dissolved in ethanol and treated with a solution of $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ (2 mole) containing sodium acetate (3 mole). The mixture was heated on a water bath for about one hour. On pouring in water, 2-hydroxy-5-methylpropiophenone-oxime (hmp-oxime) separated out, which was recrystallized from dilute alcohol.

Preparation of complexes :

The complexes were prepared according to methods described earlier^{8b}. Ethanolic solution of the respective ligand and the aqueous solution of $\text{VO}\text{SO}_4\cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were mixed together in 2 : 1 molar ratio as required. The coloured complex separated out instantaneously. It was filtered, washed with water and 50% ethanol and dried

over P_2O_5 in vacuum desiccator. The purity of the complexes was checked by elemental analyses.

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